

Adapted Mandate Assessment Checklist for risk benefit communication - test version

EFSA Working Group on Social Research Methods and Advice

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TEST VERSION

ADAPTED MANDATE ASSESSMENT CHECKLIST FOR USE IN RISK BENEFIT COMMUNICATION PLANNING

Working document for testing of risk benefit communication planning tools related to future requests for risk benefit assessments that EFSA receives

1. BACKGROUND

The EFSA Scientific Committee is in the process of revising its 2010 Guidance on Risk Benefit Assessment of Food (RBA).¹ The Terms of Reference of the revised guidance document indicated that it “includes advice on how social science can inform communication of human health RBA”. A section on Risk-Benefit Communication was included in the draft Revised Guidance on Risk Benefit Assessment of Food, made available for public consultation in February-March 2024. This document was prepared by the EFSA Working Group on Social Research Methods and Advice². It describes one of the supporting tools for risk benefit communication planning identified in the draft Guidance: Pre-Assessment.

EFSA’s approach to risk communication planning and strategy development (Vrbos et al., 2023), follow the structure of the International Risk Governance Center (IRGC) conceptual framework for understanding risk governance (Florin and Bürkler, 2017; Florin and Parker, 2020). The IRGC framework covers the entire risk analysis process and includes various steps and cross-sectional aspects:

1. Pre-assessment covers the identification and framing of the problem;
2. Appraisal concerns the assessment of the technical and perceived causes and consequences of the risk-benefit;
3. Characterisation and evaluation refer to making a judgment about the risk-benefit and the need to manage it;
4. Management indicates the process of deciding on and implementing risk management options.

Given EFSA’s remit as food safety risk assessor, the available tools cover the first two steps only: Pre-Assessment and Appraisal (Concern Assessment). This document focuses on the **Pre-Assessment - Screening phase** for risk benefit communication planning.

¹ Self-tasking mandate proposed by the Scientific Committee on the update of the EFSA Guidance for the Risk Benefit Assessment of foods -

<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/question/EFSA-Q-2022-00211>

² <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/science/scientific-committee-and-panels/comco#working-groups>

2. PRE-ASSESSMENT – SCREENING

According to the IRGC framework, pre-assessment aims at identifying the diverse views and interests in relation to a risk benefit question and the issues that need to be covered. It serves as a frame for how to assess, manage and communicate throughout the risk benefit analysis.

It begins with a “Pre-screening” step designed to shortlist requests of likely risk benefit communication potential and filter those less likely to require such support (e.g. particularly technical requests or those that affect a limited population or group of stakeholders). The second step is called “Mandates assessment” during which more structured insights are gathered in three critical areas for communication planning: i) the nature of the topic; ii) knowledge and perceptions; and iii) institutional and stakeholder interest. EFSA developed a checklist of yes/no questions linked to a decision tree for the evaluation of risk assessment questions (Vrbos et al., 2023). This has been adapted for risk benefit analysis, in particular, to understand if the risks and benefits are related to similar/unrelated health effects, to other types of risks and benefits (e.g. socio-economic, environmental), who is affected in these cases, and what is known about the perceptions of the potential risks and benefits (both human health related and other types).

The insights resulting from use of the checklist are then processed using a decision tree, resulting in one of several recommendations, e.g. proactive or reactive communication, ongoing monitoring or no communication action needed. Highly sensitive issues may also be prioritised for further evaluation in the successive stage (called Appraisal in the IRGC framework) through a “Concern assessment” which goes into greater depth about the related perceptions and societal dynamics.

3. ADAPTED MANDATE ASSESSMENT CHECKLIST

This version is adapted from the mandate assessment checklist described in Vrbos et al. (2023), with the following differences:

- Criterion 1 – the question has been modified to include human-health benefits as well as risks.
- Criterion 2 – the question is new and refers to non-human health related risks and benefits such as socio-economic, cultural or environmental³ factors that would not necessarily form part of a risk benefit assessment performed by EFSA. This question replaces a question on animal health/plant health in the original checklist.
- Criterion 9 has been revised to include reference to human health-related benefits as well as risks.
- Criterion 10 is a new question. It refers to known societal concerns about non-human health-related risks/benefits related to the hazard/hazard.

³ The updated draft EFSA Guidance on Risk Benefit Assessment of Food (pending release for public consultation) explicitly notes that environmental factors are out of the scope of the document although EFSA performs environmental risk assessments in some food safety areas, e.g. pesticides, feed additives.

TABLE 1 ADAPTED MANDATE ASSESSMENT CHECKLIST

CRITERION	YES/NO
NATURE OF THE TOPIC	
1. Are there both human-health related risks and benefits linked to the hazard/food? ⁴	
2. Are there non-human health-related risks or benefits linked to the hazard/food (e.g. environmental, socio-economic)?	
3. Is the hazard/food man-made (as opposed to naturally occurring)?	
4. Is the risk/benefit emerging/unknown?	
5. Is this the first time EFSA will assess the risk/benefit?	
6. Is this an urgent request or a Rapid Outbreak Assessment?	
7. Is this an assessment of a risk/benefit that is commonly present in everyday diets or in general a ubiquitous substance?	
8. Does this topic have the potential to communicate the benefits of EFSA’s work (highlighting one or more of its values) or the importance of the EU’s food safety system?	
KNOWLEDGE AND PERCEPTIONS	
9. Do the human health risks/benefits have characteristics that are known to cause societal concern?	
10. Do the non-human health-related risks/benefits have characteristics that are known to cause societal concern?	
11. Has the topic gained significant visibility among the target population based on media exposure to date or is it a prominent topic on social media?	
12. Are there known disagreements or diverging views on this topic (among scientists, within society groups, between scientists and society)?	
13. Are there known uncertainties related to this topic?	
14. Does this topic have the potential to negatively affect EFSA’s reputation (i.e., could EFSA be questioned in terms of conflict of interest or level of transparency etc.)?	

⁴ It is useful for audience analysis to indicate the affected populations and if they relate to the same/related health outcomes. For example, same = reduced vs enhanced brain development, different = increased liver disease risk vs reduced cardiovascular disease risk. (N.B. EFSA’s Scientific Committee considers reduction of health risks to be a health benefit.)

15. Does available social research evidence (e.g., Flash Polls, Eurobarometer, other recent studies) highlight the topic as an area of concern?

INSTITUTIONAL AND STAKEHOLDER INTEREST

16. Is this topic of interest, a priority for the European Commission and/or has risk management implications?

17. Is this topic of interest, a priority for the European Parliament?

18. Is this topic of interest or concern for Member States' authorities?

19. Is this topic of interest or concern for the civil society (e.g., consumers, NGOs or other interest organisations)?

20. Is this topic of interest or concern for the scientific community?

21. Can the assessment result in policy changes and/or have market impact?

Once the checklist is completed, the adapted Mandates decision tree (Figure 1) guides the next steps. The critical change to the existing decision tree described in Vrbos et al. (2023) involves the addition of a trigger (Criterion 2) for coordinated communication by risk assessors and risk managers. In practice, risk communication by risk assessors such as EFSA are coordinated with risk managers in the European Commission and Member States. Therefore, this trigger represents a reinforced recommendation for the two branches of risk benefit analysis to work closely on risk benefit communication when targeting citizens.

The revised checklist is designed for risk assessor organisations such as EFSA and its counterparts in Member States. However, the tool can be used by risk managers and public authorities in developing their risk benefit communication strategies.

FIGURE 1 ADAPTED MANDATE ASSESSMENT DECISION TREE

Instructions: Complete the checklist, assessing the mandate across all 21 criteria. Then follow the decision tree below, considering **"Nature of the topic"** (criteria 1-8) as the starting point. RA = risk assessor, RM = risk manager.

REFERENCES

Florin, M.V. and Bürkler, M. T. (2017). Introduction to the IRGC risk governance framework, revised edition. Lausanne: EPFL International Risk Governance Center. doi.org/10.5075/epfl-irgc-233739

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